

UNISEL THESIS FORMAT AUDIT CHECKLIST
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This detailed checklist is for the Centre for Graduate Studies (CGS) and supervisors to verify formatting compliance of postgraduate theses before viva voce and final submission. It ensures professional presentation and adherence to the official Thesis Formatting Guideline (Latest Edition-CGS website)

SECTION A – GENERAL REQUIREMENTS

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (v)	Remarks
A	A1-1	Thesis written entirely in English or Bahasa Melayu.		
A	A1-2	Language must be formal, consistent, and grammatically correct.		
A	A1-3	Use Times New Roman font.		
A	A1-4	Main text 12 pt.		
A	A1-5	Maintain consistent spelling variant (British or American).		
A	A1-6	Avoid mixing languages in the body text.		
A	A1-7	Headings and proper nouns follow disciplinary conventions.		
A	A2-1	Use A4 (210×297 mm) white simile 80 gsm paper.		
A	A2-2	Print on both sides (two-sided).		
A	A2-3	Paper quality must be uniform throughout all copies.		
A	A3-1	Maintain consistent margins on all pages.		
A	A3-2	Left margin 4.0 cm; Right, Top, Bottom 2.5 cm.		
A	A3-3	All tables and figures fit within the margins.		
A	A4-1	Use single typeface throughout the document.		

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (v)	Remarks
A	A4-2	Main body text 12 pt.		
A	A4-3	Chapter titles 14 pt bold.		
A	A4-4	Subheadings 12 pt bold.		
A	A4-5	Footnotes and table text minimum 8–10 pt.		
A	A5-1	Main text uses 1.5 line spacing.		
A	A5-2	Abstract, tables, figure captions, long quotes, footnotes, references, appendices use single spacing.		
A	A5-3	No blank line between subtitle and first paragraph.		
A	A6-1	Text fully justified.		
A	A6-2	Do not indent first line of paragraph (block style).		
A	A6-3	Leave one blank line between paragraphs.		
A	A7-1	Count and number every page properly.		
A	A7-2	Preliminary pages use lower-case Roman numerals (i, ii, iii ...).		
A	A7-3	Title page counted as i but number not printed.		
A	A7-4	Main text uses Arabic numerals (1, 2, 3 ...) starting from Chapter 1.		
A	A7-5	First page of Chapter 1 counted but number not printed.		
A	A7-6	Page numbers top-right corner, 10 pt, 1.25 cm from top and 2.5 cm from right.		
A	A8-1	Text orientation portrait; landscape allowed for large tables or figures.		
A	A8-2	Maintain consistent header and footer layout.		
A	A9-1	Thesis word count within programme range.		
A	A9-2	Master (Research): 30 000–50 000 words.		
A	A9-3	Doctorate: 50 000–80 000 words (adjust per programme standard).		
A	A10-1	Printing must be high quality and uniform throughout.		
A	A10-2	Use laser or inkjet printer with black ink.		

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (v)	Remarks
A	A10-3	Ensure consistent ink darkness on all pages.		
A	A11-1	Proposal copies use spiral binding.		
A	A11-2	Viva copies use soft cover.		
A	A11-3	Final copies use hardcover Buckram with gold lettering 18 pt.		
A	A12-1	Cover must include title, name, and university.		
A	A12-2	Use Buckram material.		
A	A12-3	Colour by level of study – PhD: Maroon; EdD: Light Brown; Master: Dark Brown.		
A	A12-4	Title in uppercase gold 18 pt font.		
A	A13-1	Spine displays candidate name, degree, year.		
A	A13-2	Gold block font 18 pt, single line format (e.g., NORAZAH Master in Science 2025).		

SECTION B – ORGANIZATION OF THESIS

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (v)	Remarks
B	B1-1	Author’s Declaration includes originality, classification, copyright, and student signature.		
B	B1-2	Heading 14 pt bold centred.		
B	B1-3	Body text 12 pt, 1.5 spacing, justified.		
B	B1-4	No page number printed.		
B	B2-1	Supervisor’s Declaration includes approval and quality confirmation.		
B	B2-2	Heading 14 pt bold centred.		
B	B2-3	Body 12 pt, 1.5 spacing, justified; no page number.		
B	B3-1	Declaration of Co-operation included when external data/organizations involved.		
B	B3-2	Heading 14 pt bold centred; body 12 pt, 1.5 spacing.		
B	B3-3	Include institutional letterhead or stamp where required.		
B	B4-1	Certification of Examination lists Dean CGS and examiners.		

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (✓)	Remarks
B	B4-2	Heading 14 pt bold; text 12 pt; 1.5 spacing; justified; no page number.		
B	B5-1	Title Page contains title, author, award statement, faculty, university, month/year.		
B	B5-2	Text bold, 12 pt, centred; double spacing; no page number (counted as i).		
B	B6-1	Dedication optional; one paragraph only.		
B	B6-2	Single spacing, centred, 12 pt font, max one page.		
B	B7-1	Acknowledgement optional; brief gratitude statement.		
B	B7-2	Single spacing, justified, 12 pt; heading 14 pt bold centred; max one page.		
B	B8-1	Abstract (English) ≤ 500 words; single paragraph.		
B	B8-2	Includes problem, objectives, methods, results, conclusion, contribution.		
B	B8-3	Single spacing; justified; 12 pt; no indentation; Roman page numbers.		
B	B8-4	English abstract appears first if thesis language is English.		
B	B9-1	Abstrak (Bahasa Melayu) ≤ 500 words; accurate translation of English.		
B	B9-2	Single paragraph; italic 12 pt; single spacing; justified.		
B	B9-3	English abstract in italic if main thesis is Bahasa Melayu.		
B	B10-1	Table of Contents lists all pages accurately with page numbers.		
B	B10-2	Heading 14 pt bold centred; 12 pt single spacing; right-aligned page numbers.		
B	B10-3	Ensure titles match exactly those in text.		
B	B11-1	List of Tables provided with correct page numbers.		
B	B11-2	Heading 14 pt bold; 12 pt single spacing; right-aligned page numbers.		
B	B12-1	List of Figures included and formatted same as List of Tables.		
B	B13-1	List of Symbols/Abbreviations included in alphabetical order.		
B	B13-2	12 pt font; single spacing; omit universal units.		
B	B14-1	List of Appendices (optional) includes titles and page numbers.		
B	B14-2	Label Appendix A, B, etc. 12 pt single spacing.		

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (✓)	Remarks
B	B15-1	Body/Text includes main chapters 1–6 organized logically.		
B	B15-2	Each chapter starts on a new page.		
B	B15-3	Chapter heading all caps 14 pt bold centred.		
B	B15-4	First page of Chapter 1 counted but not numbered.		
B	B15-5	Sub-section numbering up to 4 levels; consistent format.		
B	B16-1	Chapter 1 includes Background, Problem Statement, Objectives, Questions, Scope, Significance, Structure.		
B	B16-2	Use clear subheadings; 12 pt 1.5 spacing justified.		
B	B16-3	Ensure objectives align with methods and results.		
B	B17-1	Chapter 2 provides critical literature review and framework.		
B	B17-2	Organize by themes or chronology; 12 pt 1.5 spacing.		
B	B17-3	Use recent sources (≤ 5 years) plus seminal works.		
B	B18-1	Chapter 3 details design, sample, instruments, procedures, analysis, ethics.		
B	B18-2	Provide sufficient detail for replication.		
B	B18-3	Use subheadings for each component; 12 pt 1.5 spacing.		
B	B18-4	Include diagrams or flowcharts where helpful.		
B	B19-1	Chapter 4 reports findings objectively by research questions.		
B	B19-2	Present summary then tables/figures; use past tense.		
B	B19-3	Number tables/figures by chapter (e.g., Table 4.1).		
B	B19-4	Ensure tables/figures referenced in text.		
B	B20-1	Chapter 5 discusses results vs. literature and theory.		
B	B20-2	Address implications, limitations, and reliability.		
B	B21-1	Chapter 6 summarizes findings and contributions.		
B	B21-2	Provide recommendations and future research suggestions.		
B	B21-3	Each conclusion supported by findings.		

SECTION C – TABLES, FIGURES, EQUATIONS & CITATIONS

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (✓)	Remarks
C	C1-1	Tables numbered by chapter in order of appearance.		
C	C1-2	Caption above table; bold 12 pt centred (single line).		
C	C1-3	If caption > 1 line, left-align caption.		
C	C1-4	Table font 10–12 pt; single spacing.		
C	C2-1	Tables placed near first mention in text.		
C	C2-2	Centre tables within margins; one blank line before and after.		
C	C2-3	For wide tables use landscape orientation maintaining pagination.		
C	C3-1	Tables have clear labels and units; avoid excess decimals.		
C	C3-2	Use horizontal lines only; avoid vertical gridlines.		
C	C3-3	Provide source below table (e.g., Source: Shi et al., 2020).		
C	C4-1	Figures include charts, diagrams, photos, maps.		
C	C4-2	Caption below figure; bold 12 pt centred.		
C	C4-3	If caption > 2 lines, left-align caption.		
C	C5-1	Figures placed near first mention and readable.		
C	C5-2	Centre figure within margins; one blank line above and below caption.		
C	C5-3	Maintain consistent scaling; no stretching.		
C	C6-1	Figures min 300 dpi or vector format.		
C	C6-2	Embedded images include caption and alt text (if possible).		
C	C7-1	Cite figure sources below figure in italic 10 pt.		
C	C7-2	Obtain permission for reproduced/adapted figures.		
C	C8-1	Use Equation Editor for mathematical expressions.		
C	C8-2	Equations centred; numbered on right (e.g., (3.6)).		

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (✓)	Remarks
C	C8-3	Define all symbols on first use; variables italicized.		
C	C9-1	In-text citations use APA 7th format.		
C	C9-2	Include page number for direct quotes.		
C	C10-1	Cross-references for tables/figures use automated tools.		
C	C10-2	Refer by number in text (e.g., see Table 4.1).		

SECTION D – REFERENCES (APA 7th Edition)

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (✓)	Remarks
D	D1-1	Use APA 7th Edition style consistently.		
D	D1-2	Reference list 12 pt single spacing with hanging indent 0.5 inch.		
D	D1-3	List in alphabetical order by surname.		
D	D2-1	Use author-date citation format for paraphrase and quotes.		
D	D2-2	Three or more authors → use “et al.”.		
D	D3-1	Journal article entry includes authors, year, title, journal, volume, issue, pages, DOI.		
D	D3-2	Example format provided for reference list.		
D	D4-1	Books include author, year, title (italic), edition, publisher.		
D	D5-1	Edited book chapters include chapter author, year, editors, book title, pages, publisher.		
D	D6-1	Conference papers include author, year, title, conference name, pages, publisher/DOI.		
D	D7-1	Websites list author/organization, year, title, URL, retrieval date if needed.		
D	D8-1	Include DOI where available; otherwise stable URL.		
D	D8-2	Ensure links are live and correct.		

SECTION E – SUBMISSION, CORRECTIONS & ENDORSEMENT

Section	Item Code	Checklist Description	Check (✓)	Remarks
E	E1-1	Submit Application for Viva ≥ 3 months before intended date.		
E	E1-2	Use official CGS form signed by supervisor with progress reports attached.		
E	E2-1	Submit required soft- or perfect-bound copies for viva.		
E	E2-2	Provide five identical copies including submission form.		
E	E3-1	After viva, submit corrected copy with list of corrections.		
E	E3-2	Bind corrected copy comb/spiral for checking.		
E	E3-3	Include “List of Corrections” with page and paragraph details.		
E	E4-1	After acceptance, submit two hardbound copies (Buckram).		
E	E4-2	Include one softcopy (PDF via CD/USB) with all signatures and approvals.		
E	E5-1	Final checklist signed and dated by student and supervisor.		
E	E5-2	Names and signatures clearly printed with date fields.		
E	E5-3	Attach completed checklist with final submission.		

Please Visit our website or email us for more information:

<https://cgs.unisel.edu.my/> Email: cgs@unisel.edu.my

Social Media

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